

Summative Assessment of Mathematics: New Directions

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This paper outlines findings of a recent review of new directions in summative assessment (Shiel, 2022), prepared in the context of informing a new Literacy, Numeracy and Digital Literacy Strategy in Ireland. It looks at how summative assessment can be defined, the application of technology to summative assessment, and emerging trends in reporting. Links between formative and summative assessment are also considered.

Keywords: summative assessment, computer-based assessments, reporting

Introduction

Summative assessment can be defined as ‘the assessment of students that occurs at the end of a period of instruction. [It] provides a holistic measurement of an individual’s knowledge, skills and dispositions. . . Summative assessment consists of a variety of different formats from multiple-choice exams to research papers to portfolios of student work.’ (Nicholas, 2018, p. 1634).

In the Irish context, summative assessment relates to assessments such as the National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics (NAREM) and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), both of which are used to set national targets for student performance in literacy and numeracy and are essentially low-stakes assessments for most stakeholders. It also encompasses the standardised tests that are currently administered to pupils in the Second, Fourth and Sixth classes in primary schools, which are sometimes viewed as high-stakes, though certainly not to the same extent as census-based national or state-level assessments in Australia and the United States, where outcomes may also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of schools and teachers in promoting student achievement.

Summative assessment often enjoys a higher status than formative assessment, and this gives rise to the possibility that teaching and learning will focus more on preparing students for summative assessment, with less attention or recognition given to formative assessment. O’Leary et al. (2019) have argued that summative assessments should provide more formative information, especially for at-risk groups such as disadvantaged students, students for whom English is an additional language, and students with special educational needs. In the future, it is likely that formative and summative assessment will merge to a greater extent, particularly as technology facilitates the scoring of more complex assessment tasks. Looney (2019) has noted that electronic scoring systems can now score complex cognitive tasks such as problem solving and student collaboration on constructed response formats, enabling the use of more complex and real-life tasks in summative assessment.

Technology and Summative Assessment

In recent years, most international large-scale summative assessments, such as Trends in International Mathematics and Science (TIMSS) and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) have partially or fully transitioned to computer-based assessment. Features such as adaptive testing (where test items are more likely to

match the student's ability level) and computer-scoring of responses has led to greater efficiency in administration and scoring. Furthermore, test items have become more interactive or scenario-based, setting new challenges for students. In Ireland, schools and teachers have a choice as to whether they wish to administer computer- or paper-based standardized tests of mathematics at primary level, with separate norms available for both formats. However, features such as adaptive testing have yet to be incorporated.

A recent international development has been the use of interim summative assessments to generate formative assessment information. For example, interim assessment blocks (IABs) can be used throughout the school year to assess smaller bundles of content, (e.g., multiplication and division within 100; numbers and operations in base 10; time, volume and mass). In some cases, performance may be reported on the same scales as full standardised tests. Teachers may play a role in the selection of items for interim tests. Poortman and Schildkamp (2016) have provided evidence of a positive impact for Data-based Decision Making (DBDM), which involves the systematic analysis of existing data sources (such as interim assessments) within the school by teachers, to innovate teaching, curricula and school performance, and to evaluate progress.

Measures of Student Progress Over Time

In recent years, national and state-level assessment programmes in other countries have begun to report measures of student progress over time, alongside scores that reflect performance at a particular point in time. The Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS) reports on performance with reference to student growth percentiles. These enable stakeholders to evaluate growth in performance relative to an intake measure such as performance on an earlier assessment. Although student scores derived from these and other valued added models are often used to evaluate teacher and school effectiveness (a practice not without problems), they may also be of value in monitoring the progress of individual students and groups.

Interpreting Performance with Reference to Socioeconomic Status

A number of national assessment programmes also support the interpretation of test scores by taking socio-economic context into account. The Australian National Assessment Programme – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN), which is administered on an annual basis in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9, reports average performance at school level with reference to the performance of other students with similar socioeconomic backgrounds. This focus is intended to reduce competition between schools. In Scotland, post-primary schools can compare the performance of their school leavers on numeracy (based on national exams) against virtual comparators (groups of students of similar socioeconomic background). These approaches seem to be fair to both disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged schools.

Standards-Based Reporting Formats

The reporting of test scores (for example, STen scores) to parents and other stakeholders is not uncommon in assessment programmes in other countries. However, these are often accompanied by descriptors of performance. In England, parents and other

stakeholders are informed if students have reached the expected performance level for their age group, albeit based on a single cut-off score. In Massachusetts, performance is also reported on with respect to levels such as ‘partially meeting expectations’, ‘meeting expectations’, and ‘exceeding expectations’. These descriptors, if accompanied by information of what skills students have achieved, can provide stakeholders with more specific, standards- or curriculum-based based feedback on performance and shift the focus away from discrete numeric values.

Final Remarks

There are a number of ways in which summative assessments of mathematics, including standardised tests, can be made more relevant to the needs to stakeholders:

- Expansion of the sample-based National Assessment of Mathematics (2nd and 6th classes at primary level) to include at least some computer-based assessment tasks, as part of gradual transition to full computer-based assessment.
- Reporting of individual and group progress over time (for example, via use of student growth percentiles) and contextualising aggregated student performance by controlling for socioeconomic status, when performance is reported.
- The development of short, online interim assessments across a range of aspects of mathematics, beginning at primary level; these could be used by teachers on a needs basis throughout the school year, to support instructional decision making.
- The reporting of descriptors of achievement, alongside test scores in testing programmes with a view to providing stakeholders with more contextualised feedback.
- A consideration of the most appropriate time of the year in which to administer standardised tests (O’Leary et al., 2019).

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